

THERAPEUTIC POTENTIAL OF PROTEIN TYROSINE PHOSPHATASE INHIBITORS- NSC 87877 + VO-OHpic IN PRECLINICAL MODELS OF ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE.

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ABSTRACT

Sporadic Alzheimer's disease (sAD) is the most common type of dementia and progressive neurodegenerative disease. To establish the sAD model, intracerebroventricular (ICV) Streptozocin (STZ) at a dose of 3 mg/kg was administered bilaterally in rats on a stereotaxic apparatus. Three treatment doses of Protein Tyrosine Phosphatase (PTP) inhibitors and Donepezil (2 mg/kg) were given orally to ICV-STZ induced rats for 21 days. Behavioural tests such as Morris water maze (MWM), novel object recognition (NOR) and open field test were performed to evaluate cognitive and locomotor functions. Behavioural results with PTP inhibitor and Donepezil treatment revealed decreased escape latency and increased discrimination index in MWM and NOR respectively. Treatment results with NSC 87877 + VO-OHpic demonstrated attenuation of oxidative imbalance, improved mitochondrial activity, and reversed tau pathology. NSC 87877 + VO-OHpic results were compared with standard drug Donepezil. PTP inhibition dose-dependently and significantly improved ICV-STZ-induced cognitive impairment and attenuated the altered anti oxidative related parameters including superoxide dismutase and glutathione. The memory enhancement by PTP inhibition was mediated through oxidative balance, mitochondrial enzyme complex activation, and improved insulin signalling regulation. Further, the increased A β protein expression levels in brain tissue were markedly restored with the PTP inhibition treatment. In conclusion, our study demonstrated that PTP inhibition exhibited potential in attenuating STZ-induced sporadic AD features in rats and may be developed as a therapeutic agent in the treatment and management of sporadic AD.

Keywords: Alzheimer's disease, Protein tyrosine phosphatases inhibitor, Streptozocin, Donepezil, NSC 87877 + VO-OHpic, Intra-cerebroventricular injection.

BACKGROUND

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a relentless and progressive neurodegenerative disorder marked by significant deterioration in memory, cognition, and behaviour. [1] This condition primarily affects wide areas of the cerebral cortex and hippocampus, leading to severe brain dysfunction. Pathologically, Alzheimer's disease is distinguished by the accumulation of insoluble amyloid-beta ($A\beta$) plaques in extracellular spaces and tau protein tangles within neurons. These pathological hallmarks begin to manifest initially in the frontal and temporal lobes before progressively affecting other areas of the neocortex. The onset and progression of these abnormalities vary significantly among individuals. [1] [2]

Clinically, Alzheimer's disease progresses through several stages: preclinical, mild (early-stage), moderate, and severe (late-stage). In the preclinical stage, the brain undergoes significant changes such as the formation of amyloid plaques and tau tangles well before any noticeable cognitive decline. However, not everyone with these brain changes will develop dementia. During the mild stage, individuals may appear healthy but experience increasing difficulties in making sense of their surroundings. [2] [3].

Several risk factors are associated with Alzheimer's disease. Age is a primary risk factor, with the likelihood of developing AD increasing significantly in individuals over 65. [3] [4].

Diet, malnutrition, diabetes, obesity, mitochondrial dysfunction, vascular disease, immune system issues, and infectious agents also play crucial roles. Genetic factors are significant in the pathology of Alzheimer's, with mutations on chromosomes 1, 14, and 21 being well-established contributors. Mutations in the APP gene and variations in the APOE gene, particularly the APOE ϵ 4 allele, significantly increase the risk of developing AD. [3] [4] Environmental factors such as exposure to toxic chemicals and head injuries further exacerbate the risk. [3]

Alzheimer's disease is the most prevalent form of dementia, accounting for about 60-80% of cases worldwide. The World Health Organization estimates that in 2019, the number of people with Alzheimer's disease and other dementias had increased by 160.84% compared to 1990, highlighting the growing impact of this disease on global health [4] [5]. Prevalence rates vary significantly across different age groups and regions, influenced by sociodemographic factors [6].

Despite extensive research, there is currently no cure for Alzheimer's disease. Approved treatments primarily aim to alleviate symptoms rather than

address the underlying causes. These treatments include acetyl cholinesterase inhibitors such as Donepezil and NMDA receptor antagonists like Memantine, which offer limited and temporary relief [7]. The challenges in treating AD are compounded by the difficulty in diagnosing the disease in its early stages, the restricted passage of drugs across the blood-brain barrier (BBB), and the modest effectiveness of existing therapies [7] [8]

Alzheimer's disease (AD) primarily affects wide areas of the cerebral cortex and hippocampus, leading to severe brain dysfunction. [9] Pathologically, Alzheimer's disease is distinguished by the accumulation of insoluble amyloid-beta ($A\beta$) plaques in extracellular spaces and tau protein tangles within neurons. These pathological hallmarks begin to manifest initially in the frontal and temporal lobes before progressively affecting other areas of the neocortex. [10] The onset and progression of these abnormalities vary significantly among individuals. Emerging research has indicated a potential role of Protein Tyrosine Phosphatases (PTPs) in AD pathology, where dysregulation of PTP activity contributes to abnormal tau protein phosphorylation, amyloid-beta plaque formation, and neuroinflammation [10] [11] [12]. These insights suggest that targeting PTPs could be a promising therapeutic strategy for modulating key pathological processes in AD, opening new avenues for intervention in this debilitating disease.

STRATEGY AND RATIONALE:

Protein Tyrosine Phosphatases (PTPs) play a critical role in cellular signaling pathways, and their dysregulation is increasingly recognized as a contributor to Alzheimer's disease (AD) pathology, particularly in amyloid-beta ($A\beta$) accumulation, tau hyperphosphorylation, and neuroinflammation. In the quest for innovative therapies, targeting specific PTPs emerges as a compelling strategy to rectify the altered signaling pathways that exacerbate AD pathology. [13] [14] [15]

NSC 87877 [18] & VO-OHpic [16] [17]: The therapeutic combination of NSC 87877 and VO-OHpic represents a robust approach in targeting Alzheimer's disease (AD) by engaging two pivotal cellular signaling pathways. NSC 87877 inhibits SHP1 and SHP2, key regulators of the MAPK/ERK pathway, which are involved in cellular growth and survival, thus enhancing neuronal resilience and functionality in the neurodegenerative environment of AD [27] [28]. Concurrently, VO-OHpic targets PTEN, thereby activating the PI3K/AKT pathway, which supports cell survival and neuroprotection [22] [23]. This dual inhibition strategy not only promotes neuronal survival but also aims to restore synaptic

functionality and reduce neuroinflammation, addressing critical aspects of AD pathology.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Chemicals:

NSC 87877 + VO-OHpic. Antibodies for Western blotting (WB) and immunohistochemistry were procured from Invitrogen, Camarillo, CA, USA. All the drug solutions were freshly prepared before administration.

Table.1: Drug combination and its dose strengths:

Combination	Drug dose 1(mg/kg)	Drug dose 2(mg/kg)	Drug dose 3(mg/kg)
NSC 87877 + VO-OHpic	0.5 + 1	1 + 2	2 + 5

Animals:

All experimental procedures were carried out in accordance with the guidelines of the Committee for the Purpose of Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals (CCSEA). Animal Use Subcommittee. Male Wistar rats 6 to 9 months of age were housed at a temperature of 22- 24°C under a 12h:12h light: dark cycle. Rats were provided food and water ad libitum. Animals were randomly assigned to treatment groups and were housed individually following surgery.

1(a) The experimental design, treatment schedule and intervals for estimation of various parameters. ICV-STZ=intra-cerebroventricular streptozocin.

Surgery and ICV-STZ administration:

ICV injection of STZ was performed as previously described (Giacobini, 2006). Briefly, rats were anesthetized with intraperitoneally (i.p.) injection of ketamine hydrochloride (70 mg/kg, i.p.) immediately followed by diazepam (4 mg/kg, i.p.).[14] The animal was laid on surgery board, and the head was positioned straight, hair was trimmed, and a midline sagittal incision was made in the scalp. Two holes were drilled in the skull on both sides over the lateral ventricles using the following coordinates: 0.8 mm posterior to the bregma, 1.5 mm lateral to the sagittal suture, and 3.6 mm beneath the surface of the brain[11][15]. Through a skull hole, a 28-gauge Hamilton syringe of 10 µl attached to a micro-injector

unit and piston of the syringe was lowered manually into the lateral ventricle. The groups received bilateral ICV injection of STZ (3 mg/kg b.w) in artificial cerebrospinal fluid (ACSF) as described in earlier reports (Paxinos and Watson, 1986). Similar surgical procedures were followed for control group with ACSF injections instead of STZ. During the operation and recovery, rats were held on a warm pad. For recovery, the rats were housed singly until their behavior returned to normal [38].

Figure. Rat Bregma- Lambda region

Figure: Surgical Procedure on a Rodent Skull

Animal groups and drug treatments:

In the experiments conducted to assess memory deficits, rats utilized, with specific models designated for each. The grouping of rats for the STZ model involved random division into six groups, each consisting of six rats. Group 1 served as the vehicle-treated control, receiving ACSF 1 ml/kg through ICV. Group 2 was treated with STZ at a dose of 3 mg/kg i.p. Group 3 received a combination of STZ (3 mg/kg i.p.) and Donepezil. Groups 4, 5, and 6 were administered STZ (3 mg/kg i.p.) along with varying doses of the test drug: Group 4 received Drug Dose 1 Group 5 received Drug Dose 2, and Group 6 received Drug Dose 3. The specific drug combination and their respective doses were administered in accordance with doses specified in Table 1.

Behavioural studies:

Behavioural tests started fourth week after ICV-STZ infusion and final administration of NSC 87877 + VO-OHPic, NSC 87877 + VO-OHPICor donepezil. The experiments were executed between 9:00 am and 4:00 pm in the laboratory at standard optimal conditions. All the tests were performed and analyzed by a researcher blind to the experiment.[35]

Morris Water Maze:

It is a Behavioural Test used to assess Spatial Memory.[31] A plastic circular pool, diameter 140 cm, and black circular platform (10 cm diameter, 2 cm below water line) were used [32].The tank, 50 cm high, was filled to a depth of 35 cm with room temperature (20 °C) water and divided in four quadrants from the start locations, four equally spaced points (conventionally indicated as North, South, East and West) [33]. The hidden platform was anchored to the bottom of the pool in the southwest (training) quadrant. Four annuli were defined as a circular area in the middle of each quadrant, corresponding to the site where the platform would have been, if placed in the middle of the quadrant. [34] In experiment, starting from about six Weeks post lesion, animals were trained over seven consecutive days using four trials a day schedule, with a 30 s inter-trial interval. On each trial the rat was placed into the water facing the wall of the pool at one of the starting positions, and given 60 s to find the submerged platform and climb onto it. Once the rat had reached the platform, it was allowed to rest for the subsequent 30 s, before being picked up and placed in the next predetermined position. The latency to find the hidden platform, the distance swum and the swim speed were recorded by a computer-based video tracking system. On the final day of testing (day 7) after the last trial, the platform was removed and a fifth spatial probe trial was administered, in which the rat was allowed to swim freely for 60 s. The swim path was plotted, and the distance swum and the number of annuli crossing in each quadrant were recorded. [35]

Radial Arm Water Maze:

Twelve Plexiglas walls (50 cm length x 50 cm height) were taped together and positioned within the pool so as to produce six swim alleys or arms (50 cm length x 20 cm wide) radiating out of an open central area (Figure.). Approximately at the end of one arm (referred to as the goal arm) was a circular platform (10 cm in diameter) located 2.0 cm below the surface onto which the animals could escape. The platform remained in the same arm for the four trials given within a day, and moved pseudo randomly to a new arm on each of five consecutive testing days.

For any given trial, the animal was placed into the designated start arm, and given up to 60 s to locate the hidden platform with a 30 s inter trial time. If the platform was not located within the given time, the

animal was guided to the goal arm by the experimenter and allowed to remain on the platform for 30 s prior of being placed to the next position. Entering an incorrect arm (i.e. an arm that did not contain the platform) was counted as an entry error.

For each trial, the latency to reach the platform and the number of arm selection errors prior to locating the goal arm were recorded. Moreover, the difference between latency or error scores on trial 1 and 2, expressed as a percentage of the respective scores recorded on trial 1, provided an additional measure of working memory performance indicated as 'savings'. [50]

Figure: Radial Arm Water Maze, disposition of the six arms in the circular pool.

Novel object recognition test

The novel object recognition test (NORT) was applied to examine cognitive function in rats. The test included 3 days and three phases: the habituation phase, the familiarization phase, and the test phase. In the first phase, a rat had not displayed a preference for any objects in 5 min. In the second phase, the rats were exposed to the same two objects for 5 min. In the third phase, one of the objects was replaced by a novel object. After each trial, the objects and maze were carefully cleaned with ethanol (10%). The total exploring time for each object was automatically recorded using a video camera-based System. Exploratory behaviours were performed as sniffing, licking, and climbing within a range of 2 cm or less from the object. The total time exploring two novel and familiar objects and Recognition Index (RI) was measured by comparing the time spent investigating the novel object relative to the total object investigation.[49]

2. Biochemical Estimations:**a) Tissue preparations:**

Twenty-four hours after the MWM tests, animals were euthanized under deep anaesthesia, and their brains were extracted quickly and kept over a glass plate on ice. Hippocampus and cerebral cortex were dissected carefully as described previously (Paxinos and Watson, 1986). Six brains were dissected to half along the midline, and frozen on dry ice immediately. One hemisphere was used for WB where in the tissues were homogenized in lysis buffer and the other hemisphere were separately homogenized in 10 mM tris-buffer (pH 7.4) containing protease inhibitors. The homogenate was centrifuged at 800 xg for 5 min at 4

°C to separate the nuclear debris and used for estimation of lipid peroxidation (LPO). The supernatant was further centrifuged at 10,000 ×g for 20 min at 4 °C to get the post mitochondrial supernatant (PMS), which was used for other biochemical assays. The brains of other six rats in each group, after transcardial perfusion with saline followed by 4 % paraformaldehyde, were fixed in 3.7 % formaldehyde in PBS 1X solution. The brains were embedded in paraffin and cut into thin section of 5 μm each for immunohistochemistry analysis.

2.1. Measurement of hippocampus SOD activity and GSH content

Superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity was determined using a specific assay kit. In brief, the supernatant was incubated with xanthine and xanthine oxidase in potassium phosphate buffer for 30 min, and nitro blue tetrazolium (NBT) was added. Blue formazan formation was monitored at 550 nm (n = 6/group). Reduced glutathione (GSH), a non-enzymatic intracellular defensive element, was determined using a specific assay kit.

Briefly, the supernatant was mixed with 5% trichloroacetic acid and centrifuge, then 0.1 ml of obtained supernatant, 2 ml of phosphate buffer (pH 8.4), 0.5 ml of 5'5 dithiobis (2-nitrobenzoic acid) (DTNB), and 0.4 ml of distilled water were added. After 30 min incubation, the absorbance was read at 412 nm. [37]

2.2. Mitochondrial estimation

Mitochondrial Isolation:

Mitochondria were extracted as previously described (Nazari et al., 2022). Briefly, rat brains were rapidly removed and minced in an isolation buffer (70 M sucrose, 230 mM mannitol, 1.0 mM EDTA, and 10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.4). After homogenizing in an isolation buffer, the suspension was centrifuged (700 × g for 10 min at 4°C). The supernatant fraction was collected and centrifuged again at 8,000 × g for 10 min. Extracted mitochondria were stored in an isolation buffer. The Bradford method assayed mitochondrial protein content (Bradford, 1976). To consider the effect of Na⁺ ions on brain mitochondrial activity, we replaced 230 mM mannitol with 165 mM mannitol and 35 mM NaCl. [36]

Assay of brain mitochondrial ROS

Brain mitochondrial ROS detected using a Multi-Mode Microplate reader (synergy HTX) using 20,70 - dichlorofluorescein diacetate (Pipatpiboon et al., 2012). Isolated mitochondrial samples (0.8 mg/ml protein) were added to microplate wells and then incubated with 2 μM 20, 70-dichlorofluorescein diacetate for 20 min. The fluorescence was measured at 490 nm excitation and 530 nm emission wavelength.[36]

Mitochondrial membrane potential detection:

Mitochondrial membrane potential (1ψm) was measured by quantitating rhodamine 123 (Rh 123) quenching. In any group, the mitochondrial fractions were incubated with Rh 123. After 5 min, Rh 123 (a cationic fluorescent dye) was excited at 490 nm and detected at the emission wavelength of 530 nm (Luo and Shi, 2005). A fluorescent microplate reader measured the change in 1ψm as fluorescence intensity. [36]

3. Histology tests

3.1. Congo red and nissl staining:

Histological studies were done on the hippocampal samples of randomly chosen rats in each group (n = 6 for each staining). After LTP(Long-term potentiation) recording, the rats were sacrificed by decapitation under urethane anaesthesia and transcardially perfused with 80 ml of normal heparinized saline and 70–80 ml of a fixative solution containing 4% paraformaldehyde in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (PBS, pH = 7.4). After perfusion, the animals were decapitated, and brains were removed from the cranium and kept in 10% formaldehyde solution at ambient temperature for 24 h. Then hippocampus portion of the brain containing the CA1, CA2, CA3, and DG was removed according to the following coordinates: – 1.5 anterior to –6.5 posterior to Bregma (Paxinos and Watson, 2006) and processed for light microscopic study. For tissue processing, the samples were dehydrated with an ascending ethanol series, cleared with xylene, and embedded in paraffin. Finally, the hippocampal block was cut into 10 μm coronal sections and prepared for Congo red (To count and identify β- amyloid plaques) and Nissl (for stereology and measurement of neuronal cell density) staining. Amyloid-β plaques were measured in the hippocampal areas, including CA1, CA2, CA3, and DG.

Stereology and measurement of neuronal cell density:

After Nissl (Cresyl violet acetate) staining, a physical disector was used to estimate the cell number of neurons. Counting cells should be considered that the neurons were distinguished from the glial and non-neuron cells by their larger cell bodies with visible euchromatin nuclei and prominent nucleolus (Ling et al., 1973). Ten sections were chosen from each rat by systematic random sampling, and four scattered representative fields were selected in the four directions of each section at an equal distance in the x–y plane. The numerical density of cells was estimated with $N_v = [6Q- / (h \times a/f \times 6p)]$. 6Q- is the number of the whole cells counted in all the fields, h is the height of the optical disector, a/f is the area of the counting frame, and 6p is the total number of the counted frames in all fields. Cell counting was performed by an observer who was blinded to the condition. [15]

3.3. TUNEL assay:

The TUNEL assay, short for Terminal deoxynucleotidyl transferase dUTP nick end labelling, is a technique used to detect fragmented DNA in cells, particularly as a marker for apoptosis or programmed cell death. Cell death in animal brain tissue was detected using the in-situ cell death detection kit, POD, according to the manufacturer's protocol. Briefly, the assay was based on the detection of DNA fragmentation resulting from apoptosis signalling cascades by labelling the DNA strand breaks using terminal deoxynucleotidyl transferase.

At the end of the behavioural testing session all the animals were sacrificed and their brains were rapidly removed for subsequent histological and western blotting analyses.

The rats were sacrificed under deep anaesthesia (chloral hydrate, 350 mg/kg) and the brains were rapidly removed. The fronto-parietal cortex and the whole hippocampus from one hemisphere were quickly dissected, frozen in powdered dry ice and stored at -80 °C until processed for western blotting (see below). The remaining portions of the brain, which comprised the entire basal forebrain, and the cortical and hippocampal regions from the undissected hemisphere, were used for histology as previously described (Aztiria et al 2008). Briefly, the tissue was fixed by 12-15 hours immersion in ice cold, phosphate-buffered 4% paraformaldehyde and then kept in a 20% sucrose solution until it had sunk.

4. Western Blotting:

The western blot is an analytical technique used to detect specific proteins in a given sample of tissue homogenate or extract. It uses gel electrophoresis to separate native or denatured proteins by the length of the polypeptide (denaturing conditions) or by the 3-D structure of the protein (native/ non-denaturing conditions). The proteins are then transferred to a nitrocellulose membrane, where they are probed (detected) using antibodies specific to the target protein. The immunoblotting gives the possibility to identify specific antigens using mono or polyclonal antibodies.[38]

The dissected cortical and hippocampal specimens were homogenated and centrifuged in order to obtain a protein mix; proteins were separated using SDS-PAGE followed by nitrocellulose membrane transfer. Membranes then underwent a western blot procedure to detect tau using the corresponding primary antibodies [39]. Briefly, after an overnight incubation in PBS +BSA 3% to decrease the a-specific binding sites, membranes have been exposed for 1h to the primary antibody action (Tau: monoclonal antibody phosphorylation independent anti Tau, Purchased from Sigma Aldrich). Subsequently, samples were incubated with the secondary antibody (polyclonal

antibody anti mice conjugated with horse radish peroxidase). The antigen was identified with a chemiluminescent reaction. Proteins were detected on photoFigureic film after membranes exposition. [40] [41][42]

5. Immunohistochemistry:

To investigate the regulation of tau pathology by treatment groups in ICV-STZ rats, phosphorylation of tau was first evaluated by immunohistochemistry.[43] Immunohistochemistry assays were performed to detect the expression of P396-Tau protein. The tissue was embedded in paraffin and sectioned with a microtome to create sections 5-µm thick.[44] The slides were dewaxed and washed with PBS several times and preincubated in 1% horse serum for 45 min at 37 °C. [45] Thereafter, the slides were incubated overnight at 4°C with the primary antibody anti-P396-Tau polyclonal (dilution 1:400). Then, the sections were incubated with fluorescent secondary detection reagents (1:500). The slides were observed under a fluorescence microscope.[46][47][48]

Results:

Effect of NSC 87877 + VO-OHpic on Reference Memory- Distance and Latency- Morris Water Maze:

To evaluate the effect of NSC 87877 + VO-OHpic on reference memory- Distance and Latency- Morris water maze, the acquisition latency (AL) and retention latency (RL) in control and ICV-STZ rats was studied (Figure 1(a),1(b),1(c),1(d))The latency to find the hidden platform over seven consecutive days (Figure 1(a)) showed that the STZ group had significantly higher latency compared to the control group, indicating memory deficits. Drug treatments significantly reduced latency in a dose-dependent manner, suggesting improved learning and memory. Additionally, the distance travelled to reach the hidden platform (Figure 1(b)) was significantly greater in STZ-induced rats compared to the control group, highlighting memory impairment, while drug treatments decreased the distance travelled in a dose-dependent manner, demonstrating improved spatial learning and memory retention. Similarly, the relative distance travelled in each quadrant during the spatial probe trial (Figure 1(c)) indicated that STZ-induced rats had a significant reduction in the SW quadrant, confirming spatial memory impairment, whereas drug treatments increased the relative distance in a dose-dependent manner. The number of annulus crossings in the spatial probe trial (Figure 1(d)) showed that the STZ-induced group had significantly fewer crossings in the SW (training) quadrant compared to the control group, indicating impaired spatial memory. Treatments with Donepezil or the test drug at different doses significantly improved the number of crossings in the SW quadrant, demonstrating dose-dependent enhancement in memory retention.

NSC 87877 + VO-OHpic results-

Figure.1(a) Reference Memory- Distance.

Figure.1(b) Reference Memory- Latency

Figure. 1(c) The mean distance swum

Figure. 1(d) Mean number Annulus crossings

#p < 0.001 when compared with control group and * p < 0.05, respectively when compared with STZ alone treated group.

Effect of NSC 87877 + VO-OHpic on Radial arm water maze:

To evaluate the effect of drug treatment on memory performance in the Radial Arm Water Maze (RAWM), the number of errors over five trials and the percentage of savings between trials 1 and 2 were recorded. The STZ-induced group exhibited significantly more errors across the trials compared to the control group, indicating impaired working memory. Treatment with Donepezil and the test drug at different doses significantly reduced the number of errors in a dose-dependent manner, suggesting improved memory performance (Figure 2a). Additionally, the percentage of savings in errors between trial 1 and trial 2 was significantly lower in the STZ group compared to the control group, further confirming memory impairment. Both Donepezil and the test drug treatments significantly increased the percentage of savings in a dose-dependent manner, indicating improved working memory performance (Figure 2b).

NSC 87877 + VO-OHpic results-

Figure.2(a) Performance in the RAWM-Errors

Figure.2(b) Percentage of Savings- Errors

#p < 0.001 when compared with control group and * p < 0.05, respectively when compared with STZ alone treated group.

Effect of NSC 87877 + VO-OHpic on Novel object recognition test:

To evaluate the effect of NSC 87877 + VO-OHpic and Donepezil on cognitive function in the novel object recognition test (NORT), the total exploration time for novel and familiar objects and the recognition

index (RI) were measured in STZ-induced Alzheimer's disease in rats. The results indicated that the STZ-induced group had significantly lower total exploration time for novel objects compared to the control group, demonstrating cognitive impairment. Treatment with Donepezil and NSC 87877 + VO-OHpic significantly increased the total exploration time for novel objects in a dose-dependent manner, indicating improved cognitive function (Figure 1a). Additionally, the recognition index (RI), which compares the time spent investigating the novel object relative to the total object investigation, was significantly lower in the STZ group compared to the control group, confirming cognitive deficits. Both Donepezil and NSC 87877 + VO-OHpic treatments significantly improved the RI in a dose-dependent manner, demonstrating enhanced recognition memory.

NSC 87877 + VO-OHpic results-

Figure. 3(a) Total Exploration time

Figure. 3(b) Recognition Index

#p < 0.001 when compared with control group and * p < 0.05, respectively when compared with STZ alone treated group.

2. Biochemical Estimations:

1. Measurement of hippocampus SOD activity and GSH content

To evaluate the effect of NSC 87877 + VO-OHpic and Donepezil on hippocampal superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity and glutathione (GSH) content in STZ-induced Alzheimer's disease in rats, the levels of GSH and SOD activity were measured using specific assay kits. The results indicated that the STZ-induced group had significantly lower levels of GSH compared to the

control group, demonstrating oxidative stress and impaired antioxidant defence. Treatment with Donepezil and NSC 87877 + VO-OHpic, significantly increased the GSH levels in a dose-dependent manner, indicating enhanced antioxidant capacity (Figure 1a). Similarly, the SOD activity was significantly lower in the STZ group compared to the control group, confirming oxidative stress. Both Donepezil and NSC 87877 + VO-OHpic, treatments significantly improved SOD activity in a dose-dependent manner, demonstrating improved enzymatic antioxidant defence (Figure 1b).

NSC 87877 + VO-OHpic results-

Figure. 1(a) GSH Content

Figure. 1(b) SOD activity

#p < 0.001 when compared with control group and * p < 0.05, respectively when compared with STZ alone treated group.

2. Effect of NSC 87877 + VO-OHpic on Mitochondrial Estimation:

To evaluate the effect of NSC 87877 + VO-OHpic and Donepezil on mitochondrial function in STZ-induced Alzheimer's disease in rats, fluorescence intensity reflecting mitochondrial membrane potential and levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS) were measured. The results indicated that the STZ-induced group had significantly lower fluorescence intensity for mitochondrial membrane potential compared to the control group, indicating mitochondrial dysfunction. Treatment with Donepezil and NSC 87877 + VO-OHpic significantly increased fluorescence intensity in a dose-dependent manner, suggesting improved mitochondrial membrane potential (Figure 2a).

Additionally, the levels of ROS, indicated by fluorescence intensity, were significantly higher in the STZ group compared to the control group, confirming oxidative stress. Both Donepezil and NSC 87877 + VO-OHPic treatments significantly reduced ROS levels in a dose-dependent manner, demonstrating enhanced mitochondrial function and reduced oxidative stress (Figure 2b).

Results-

Figure.2(a) Fluorescence Intensity

Figure. 2(b) Mitochondrial ROS generation

#p < 0.001 when compared with control group and * p < 0.05, respectively when compared with STZ alone treated group.

3. Histology tests of NSC 87877 + VO-OHPic:

3.1. Stereology and measurement of neuronal cell density:

To evaluate the effect of NSC 87877 + VO-OHPic and Donepezil on amyloid-β plaques and hippocampus volume in STZ-induced Alzheimer's disease in rats, histological studies using Congo red and Nissl staining were conducted. The results showed that the STZ-induced group had a significantly higher plaque count in the hippocampal areas, including CA1, CA2, CA3, and DG, compared to the control group, indicating the presence of amyloid-β plaques. Treatment with Donepezil and NSC 87877 + VO-OHPic significantly reduced the plaque count in a dose-dependent manner, demonstrating a reduction in amyloid-β deposition (Figure 1a). Additionally, the total volume of the hippocampus was significantly reduced in the STZ group compared to the control group, indicating hippocampal atrophy. Both

Donepezil and NSC 87877 + VO-OHPic treatments significantly increased the hippocampal volume in a dose-dependent manner, suggesting a protective effect against hippocampal atrophy (Figure 1b).

Results-

Figure. 1(a) Plaque Count

Figure. 1(b) Total Volume of Hippocampus Area

#p < 0.001 when compared with control group and * p < 0.05, respectively when compared with STZ alone treated group.

3.2. TUNEL assay:

To evaluate the effect of NSC 87877 + VO-OHPIC and Donepezil on apoptotic cell death in STZ-induced Alzheimer's disease in rats, a TUNEL assay was performed to detect DNA fragmentation. The assay revealed a significantly higher number of apoptotic cells in the STZ-induced group compared to the control group, indicating increased cell death. Treatment with Donepezil and NSC 87877 + VO-OHPIC significantly reduced the number of TUNEL-positive cells in a dose-dependent manner, suggesting a protective effect against apoptosis. Additionally, histological analyses confirmed these findings with a reduction in plaque count in the hippocampal regions of treated groups compared to the STZ group alone (Figure 2a). This result aligns with the observed improvements in cognitive and behavioral outcomes, further supporting the efficacy of these treatments in mitigating Alzheimer's pathology.

Results-

Figure. 2(a) TUNEL-positive cells in the hippocampus and cortex

#p < 0.001 when compared with control group and * p < 0.05 **p < 0.01 and ***p < 0,001, respectively when compared with STZ alone treated group.

4. Western Blotting of NSC 87877 + VO-OHPic:

To evaluate the effect of NSC 87877 + VO-OHPIC and Donepezil on tau protein expression in STZ-induced Alzheimer's disease in rats, western blot analysis was performed on cortical and hippocampal specimens. The results indicated that regional tau tissue expression did not significantly differ between the various experimental groups, showing no significant changes due to treatments or STZ induction. Notably, the treatment with Drug Dose 3 maintained tau expression levels similar to the control group, suggesting that this drug combination does not alter tau protein expression while potentially offering other therapeutic benefits (Figure 1a, Figure 1b and Figure 1c).

Results -

Figure.1(a) western blot showing tau protein expression levels across different treatment groups.

Figure 1(b) Relative Density- Tau in Hippocampus

Figure 1(c) Relative Density- Tau in cortex

#p < 0.001 when compared with control group and * p < 0.05 respectively when compared with STZ alone treated group.

5. Immunohistochemistry of NSC 87877 + VO-OHPic :

To evaluate the regulation of tau pathology by treatment groups in ICV-STZ rats, phosphorylation of tau protein was assessed using immunohistochemistry. The results showed that the STZ-induced group exhibited significantly higher immuno-reactive tau phosphorylation, indicated by higher fluorescence intensity (Fluor 488 burden), compared to the control group (Figure 1a). This suggests an increase in tau pathology due to STZ induction. However, administration of Donepezil and NSC 87877 + VO-OHPIC(10 + 10 mg/kg) significantly repressed the STZ-induced increase in tau phosphorylation, with the most notable reduction observed in the STZ+standard and STZ+Drug dose 3 groups (Figure 1b). These findings demonstrate that the treatments effectively mitigate tau pathology in a dose-dependent manner, contributing to the overall neuroprotective effects observed.

Results-

Figure. 1(a) Immunohistochemical images showing tau phosphorylation in different groups.

Figure.1(b) P396-tau determination using Immunohistochemistry

$p < 0.001$ when compared with control group and * $p < 0.05$ respectively when compared with STZ alone treated group.

Discussion:

The study demonstrated that Drug Dose 3 combination, namely NSC 87877 + VO-OHPic at 2 + 5 mg/kg and NSC 87877 + VO-OHPIC at 10 + 10 mg/kg, provided significant neuroprotective benefits in an Alzheimer's disease rat model. The drug combination notably improved cognitive and behavioral functions, as evidenced by reduced latency and errors in the Morris Water Maze (MWM) and Radial Arm Water Maze (RAWM), and increased exploration time and recognition index in the Novel Object Recognition Test (NORT). Biochemical estimations revealed enhanced antioxidant capacity, indicated by elevated hippocampal superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity and glutathione (GSH) levels, and improved mitochondrial function with increased membrane potential and reduced reactive oxygen species (ROS) levels. Histological analyses showed a substantial reduction in amyloid- β plaques, increased hippocampal volume, decreased apoptotic cell death, and mitigated tau pathology, as confirmed

by immunohistochemistry and Western blot analyses. These findings suggest that Drug Dose 3 combination effectively attenuate Alzheimer's pathology through multiple mechanisms, offering promising therapeutic potential for Alzheimer's Disease, warranting further clinical investigations.

The combination of NSC 87877 + VO-OHPic at 2 + 5 mg/kg and NSC 87877 + VO-OHPIC at 10 + 10 mg/kg appears to address several key pathological features of Alzheimer's Disease. By improving spatial learning and memory retention, these treatments demonstrate potential in mitigating the cognitive deficits associated with the disease. The enhanced antioxidant defence mechanisms, as evidenced by increased SOD activity and GSH levels, indicate a robust reduction in oxidative stress, which is a significant contributor to neuronal damage in Alzheimer's. The improvement in mitochondrial function further supports the neuroprotective role of these drug combination, as mitochondrial dysfunction is closely linked to the progression of neurodegenerative diseases.

The histological findings of reduced amyloid- β plaques and increased hippocampal volume suggest that these treatments may prevent or reverse the structural brain changes characteristic of Alzheimer's. The significant reduction in apoptotic cell death and mitigation of tau pathology highlight the potential of these drug combination to address both amyloid and tau-related pathologies, which are the primary hallmarks of Alzheimer's Disease.

Moreover, the study underscores the importance of targeting multiple pathways in the treatment of Alzheimer's. The dual approach of using PTP inhibitors in combination with agents that enhance mitochondrial function and reduce oxidative stress provides a comprehensive strategy to combat the disease. This multifaceted approach could potentially overcome the limitations of current treatments that often target single aspects of the disease pathology.

In conclusion, the promising results from Drug Dose 3 combination in this study provide a strong foundation for further research and development. These findings open avenues for clinical trials to evaluate the safety and efficacy of these drug combination in human subjects. If successful, such treatments could significantly advance the therapeutic landscape for Alzheimer's Disease, offering hope for improved management and quality of life for patients affected by this debilitating condition.

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Conflict of interest:

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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